

Matrix Representation of Power Distribution Networks in Julia

Alejandro Garcés-Ruiz

Universidad Tecnológica de Pereira
Carrera 27 nro. 10-02 Los Álamos-Pereria-Risaralda-Colombia
www.utp.edu.co

Abstract

A power distribution network may have hundreds of nodes and hence, a systematic representation in the form of network matrices is necessary. These matrices include the incidence matrix, the nodal admittance matrix or Y_{bus} , and the nodal impedance matrix or Z_{bus} . This report shows the usage of these matrices, their mathematical properties, and their implementation in Julia. The Kron's reduction method is also described as well as the power flow equation both, in complex and real domains.

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1 Incidence matrix

A power distribution network typically consists of hundreds of nodes and lines, necessitating a structured representation that can be implemented in a programming language such as Julia. This mathematical framework derives from graph theory, a classic mathematical area funded by Euler back in the 18th century, which has been relevant in all types of computing applications, from circuit analysis to social networks [Garcés and Rodriguez-Garcia, 2019].

A graph comprises a set of nodes, denoted as \mathcal{N} , and a set of lines (a.k.a., branches or links), denoted as $\mathcal{L} \in \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}$, which establish connections between these nodes. The essential mathematical characteristics of the network primarily depend on its graph topology. To illustrate this, Figure 1 showcases three examples of power distribution networks represented as graphs. In the first example, labeled as Network a), the set of nodes is $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, and the set of branches is $\mathcal{L} = \{(1, 2), (2, 3), (2, 4)\}$. This network exhibits a radial configuration, also known as a tree, which means that there is a unique path between any pair of nodes. Conversely, in Network b), the branches $\{(2, 3), (2, 4), (4, 3)\}$ create a loop, resulting in a meshed topology. Both Network a) and b) are considered connected graphs since there are no isolated nodes, unlike Network c), which is disconnected. While a comprehensive taxonomy of graphs exists, these three instances hold particular significance for our applications.

Figure 1: Example of power distribution networks represented as graphs: a) radial, b) meshed, c) disconnected.

We can generate an oriented incidence matrix, denoted as $A = [a_{km}]$, to illustrate the relationships between nodes and lines within a power distribution network. This matrix comprises $n_{\text{lines}} = |\mathcal{L}|$ rows and $n_{\text{nodes}} = |\mathcal{N}|$ columns where each entry a_{km} is determined by the following rules: $a_{ij} = 1$ if a line i connects with the node k while departing from it; if a line i connects with the node j while arriving at it, then $a_{ij} = -1$; and if there is not connection with the node j , then $a_{ik} = 0$. The example below shows its implementation in Julia.

●● Example 1.

Let us proceed with the computation of the oriented incidence matrix for the network presented in Figure 1a) using the following Julia code:

```
using LinearAlgebra

# Define the function Incidence Matrix
function Incidence_Matrix(N::Vector,L::Vector)
    n_nodes = length(N)
    n_lines = length(L)
    A = zeros(n_lines,n_nodes)
    for (i,(k,m)) in enumerate(L)
        A[i,k] = 1
        A[i,m] = -1
    end
    return A
end

# Use the function with the following graph
N = [1,2,3,4]
L = [(1,2),(2,3),(2,4)]
A = Incidence_Matrix(N,L)
println(A)
```

The explanation of the code is the following: in the first steps, the graph defined with its corresponding sets N and L . Then, we create a function with a for-loop that takes the aforementioned rules to generate the oriented incidence matrix. The following result is obtained:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Orientation is given by the order in which lines are stored in L . Every branch i departs from $L[i][1]$ and arrives at $L[i][2]$. The same function can be used to calculate the incidence matrix for Networks b), c), or any arbitrary graph. It is only required to change arrays N and L .

Although there are multiple definitions for an incidence matrix, the approach presented herein proves more suitable for power systems applications. Notably, this matrix does not account for the ground node, despite the presence of components connecting to the ground [Molina and Rudnick, 2010]. These components are considered in the nodal-admittance matrix, but not in the incidence matrix, as expounded upon in the forthcoming section. This is a typical convention in power distribution networks that is not common in graph theory books. It is pertinent to remark that the incidence matrix exhibits a rank of n_{lines} in a connected graph, be it radial or meshed.

2 Nodal admittance and nodal impedance matrices

The oriented incidence matrix allows to systematically establish the Kirchhoff laws of the entire circuit. Branch voltages and currents are defined in vectors V_{line} and I_{line} , respectively. The directions of the currents are arbitrarily assigned based on a chosen orientation within the corresponding graph. Thus, nodal and branch voltages are related through the following expression:

$$V_{\text{line}} = AV_{\text{bus}} \quad (2)$$

For example, in Network a), depicted in Figure 1, we have the following relations:

$$v_{12} = v_1 - v_2 \quad (3)$$

$$v_{23} = v_2 - v_3 \quad (4)$$

$$v_{24} = v_2 - v_4 \quad (5)$$

which clearly hold (2) with $V_{\text{line}} = (v_{12}, v_{23}, v_{24})^\top$, $V_{\text{bus}} = (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4)^\top$ and, A given by (1). A similar argument may be employed to obtain an expression for the nodal currents. However, in this case, we require considering currents that flow through a possible component connected to ground. These components include shunt compensation and the capacitance of distribution lines (or cables). Let us consider a diagonal matrix Y_{shunt} that includes all admittance from each node to ground. Then, the nodal currents are given by the following vector:

$$I_{\text{bus}} = A^\top I_{\text{line}} + Y_{\text{shunt}} V_{\text{bus}} \quad (6)$$

Similarly, we can calculate the current in each branch from its voltage and a corresponding admittance matrix, as follows:

$$I_{\text{line}} = Y_{\text{line}} I_{\text{line}} \quad (7)$$

Where Y_{line} is a diagonal matrix with the branch admittance. Combining (2), (6) and (7) we obtain the following expression:

$$I_{\text{bus}} = Y_{\text{bus}} V_{\text{bus}} \quad (8)$$

where Y_{bus} is the nodal admittance matrix, namely:

$$Y_{\text{bus}} = A^\top Y_{\text{line}} A + Y_{\text{shunt}} \quad (9)$$

This matrix is a compendium of the Kirchhoff and Ohm laws, presented in a single expression. It relates nodal voltages with nodal currents in the entire grid, so, it is a systematic way to represent a large power distribution network.

•• Example 2.

Consider the power distribution network depicted in Figure 1 a). Each line is repented by impedances $z_{12} = 0.011 + 0.081j$, $z_{23} = 0.013 + 0.052j$ and, $z_{24} = 0.015 + 0.047j$. There is a shunt compensation in node 3 with $y_{\text{sh}} = 0.7j$. The following script calculates the nodal admittance matrix, which requires the function previously defined in Example 1:

```

N = [1, 2, 3, 4]
L = [(1, 2), (2, 3), (2, 4)]
A = Incidence_Matrix(N, L)
z_branch = [0.011+0.081im; 0.013+0.052im; 0.015+0.047im]
y_branch = diagm(1.0./z_branch)
y_shunt = diagm([0.0; 0.0; 0.8im; 0])
y_bus = A'*y_branch*A+y_shunt

```

The result is presented below:

$$Y_{\text{bus}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.65 - 12.12j & -1.65 + 12.12j & 0 & 0 \\ -1.65 + 12.12j & 12.33 - 49.53j & -4.52 + 18.10j & -6.16 + 19.31j \\ 0 & -4.52 + 18.10j & 4.52 - 17.30j & 0 \\ 0 & -6.16 + 19.31j & 0 & 6.16 - 19.31j \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Notice there the admittance is zero in those entries that represent nodes without direct connection (e.g., in positions (1,3), (1,4) and (3,4)).

Another way to calculate the nodal admittance matrix is by directly identifying the elements connected to each node. Let us consider a generic node k connected to every other node of the grid, as depicted in Figure 2. Each branch has an admittance y_{km}^{line} with $km \in \mathcal{L}$, being \mathcal{L} the set of lines. Moreover, the shunt elements connected to the ground are represented by y_k^{shunt} . Therefore, the nodal current is given by the following expression:

$$i_k = y_k^{\text{shunt}} v_k + y_{k1}^{\text{line}} (v_k - v_1) + y_{k2}^{\text{line}} (v_k - v_1) + \dots + y_{km}^{\text{line}} (v_k - v_m) + \dots + y_{kn}^{\text{line}} (v_k - v_n) \quad (11)$$

which can be organized as given below:

$$i_k = \left(y_k^{\text{shunt}} + \sum_{m=1}^n y_{km}^{\text{line}} \right) v_k - \sum_{m=1}^n y_{km}^{\text{line}} v_m \quad (12)$$

This model is general even for the case in which k is not connected to a node m . In that case, $y_{km}^{\text{line}} = 0$. Thus, we can calculate the Y_{bus} by splitting into the entries on the diagonal and the entries outside the diagonal, namely:

Figure 2: Representation of a generic node in a power grid

$$y_{km} = \begin{cases} y_k^{\text{shunt}} + \sum y_{km}^{\text{line}} & \text{for } k = m \\ -y_{km}^{\text{line}} & \text{for } k \neq m \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The following example shows the algorithm:

•• **Example 3.**

Let us calculate the Y_{bus} of the power distribution network previously analyzed in Example 2:

```
using LinearAlgebra

function calculate_ybus(L,z_branch,y_shunt)
    num_nodes = maximum(maximum(L))
    y_bus = zeros(ComplexF64,num_nodes,num_nodes)
    for (i,(k,m)) in enumerate(L)
        y_lin = 1.0/z_branch[i]
        y_bus[k,k] += y_lin
        y_bus[k,m] -= y_lin
        y_bus[m,k] -= y_lin
        y_bus[m,m] += y_lin
    end
    for (k,y) in enumerate(y_shunt)
        y_bus[k,k] += y
    end
    return y_bus
end

function main()
    L = [(1,2),(2,3),(2,4)]
    z_branch = [0.011+0.081im; 0.013+0.052im; 0.015+0.047im]
    y_shunt = [0.0; 0.0; 0.8im; 0]
    y_bus = calculate_ybus(L,z_branch,y_shunt)
    println(y_bus)
    return 0
end
```

```
end
main()
```

First, we identify the number of nodes by calculating the maximum of L . The double maximum is required because the highest number may be in the first or the second column according to the assigned current direction. Then, we create a complex vector of zeros. This vector is filled according to the rule given in (13). The iterative statement is defined by a index i , which indicates the iteration, and (k, m) which stores its contents. Notice, this code is general for power distribution networks of any size, so, we create a function from this script for later use.

Both, the formulation using the incidence matrix and the direct formulation allow identifying key properties of the nodal admittance matrix. For example, (13) indicates the Y_{bus} is weakly diagonal dominant. It is also diagonally dominant if $y_k \neq 0, \forall k \in \mathcal{N}$ (i.e., all nodes have a shunt component).

3 Kron's reduction

Kron's reduction is a mathematical technique for simplifying the representation of large power networks. It is named after the Hungarian-American engineer Gabriel Kron, who developed this method in the mid-20th century [Kron, 1942]. Its main goal is to reduce the number of nodes and branches in a power network while maintaining its essential characteristics, such as power flow and impedance relationships.

Let us consider a power system with nodes partitioned into two sets N and S , where S are those nodes in which the nodal current is zero. Therefore, the nodal admittance matrix can be separated into four block-matrices with the following voltage/current relations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ I_N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{SS} & Y_{SN} \\ Y_{NS} & Y_{NN} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_S \\ V_N \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Hence, the nodal current I_N can be obtained from the nodal voltage V_N without calculating V_S , as given in (15)

$$I_N = (Y_{NN} - Y_{NS}Y_{SS}^{-1}Y_{SN})V_N \quad (15)$$

From this equation, we can obtain a reduced admittance matrix presented below:

$$Y_{\text{kron}} = Y_{NN} - Y_{NS}Y_{SS}^{-1}Y_{SN} \quad (16)$$

Y_{kron} exactly represents all the electrical relationships between nodal voltages V_N and nodal currents I_N , being a reduced version of Y_{bus} .

•• Example 4.

Let us consider the Y_{bus} calculated in Example 3 but eliminating Nodes 1 and 3. The following code is introduced into the main function to make the Kron's reduction:

```
S = [1, 3]
N = setdiff(1:4, S)
y_kron = y_bus[N,N] - y_bus[N,S]*inv(y_bus[S,S])*y_bus[S,N]
```

First, the set S is defined, as well as the set N which is the complement of S . Next, Equation (16) is used to obtain the Kron's reduction.

•• Example 5.

Kron's reduction can be regarded as a generalization of the classic $Y - \Delta$ transformation. Consider a simple three-phase resistive load as the one depicted in Figure 3. The matrix Y_{bus} for the Y-connection is given below:

$$Y_{\text{bus}} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.0 & -2.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ -2.0 & 10.0 & -3.0 & -5.0 \\ 0.0 & -3.0 & 3.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & -5.0 & 0.0 & 5.0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Figure 3: Example of a $Y - \Delta$ transformation

its Kron's reduction is the following:

$$Y_{\text{kron}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.6 & -0.6 & -1.0 \\ -0.6 & 2.1 & -1.5 \\ -1.0 & -1.5 & 2.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

The code in Julia for the constructing the admittance matrix and its Kron's reduction is presented below:

```
using LinearAlgebra
ya = 2
yb = 3
yc = 5
y_bus = [ya -ya 0 0; -ya ya+yb+yc -yb -yc; 0 -yb yb 0; 0 -yc 0 yc]
N = [1, 3, 4]
S = [2]
y_kron = y_bus[N,N] - y_bus[N,S]*inv(y_bus[S,S])*y_bus[S,N]
```

The result is the same if the $Y - \Delta$ transformation is performed first, and then, the Y_{bus} is calculated.

4 Nodal powers and power flows

The entire state of the power distribution network can be established using nodal voltages and the nodal admittance matrix. Thus, other magnitudes such as currents, power flows and nodal powers can be easily calculated. Let us consider a generic node as the one depicted in Figure 2. The injected power in said node is $s_k^* = v_k^* i_k$ where v_k is the nodal voltage and i_k the nodal current, both complex variables (notice that s_k^* is the complex conjugate of s). This expression is equivalent to $s_k = v_k i_k^*$. The latter can be written as a function of the nodal admittance matrix, as in (8), resulting in the expression below:

$$s_k^* = v_k^* i_k \quad (19)$$

which is equivalent to

$$s_k^* = \sum_{m=1}^n y_{km} v_k^* v_m \quad (20)$$

or, in matrix form:

$$S_{\text{bus}}^* = V_{\text{bus}}^* \circ (Y_{\text{bus}} V_{\text{bus}}) \quad (21)$$

where $(^*)$ represents the complex conjugate and \circ the Hadamard product. Calculating s_k^* is more convenient than calculating, s_k since the latter requires conjugating both the voltages and the matrix Y_{bus} . The same expression can be written the real domain by defining $s_k = p_k + jq_k$, $y_{km} = g_{km} + jb_{km}$ and, $v_k = |v_k| e^{j\theta_k}$, namely:

$$p_k = \sum_{m=1}^n g_{km} |v_k| |v_m| \cos(\theta_{km}) + b_{km} |v_k| |v_m| \sin(\theta_{km}) \quad (22)$$

$$q_k = \sum_{m=1}^n g_{km} |v_k| |v_m| \sin(\theta_{km}) - b_{km} |v_k| |v_m| \cos(\theta_{km}) \quad (23)$$

Notice how simple the complex representation is, compared to the representation in the real domain.

•• Example 6.

Consider the system in Example 2 with the following nodal voltages: $v_1 = 1.0 \angle 0.0$, $v_2 = 0.9534 \angle -0.1734$, $v_3 = 0.9710 \angle -0.2262$ and, $v_4 = 0.9060 \angle -0.23017$. The following code calculates the nodal currents, and nodal power. We suppose the Y_{bus} was already calculated, as in Example 2:

```
using DataFrames
vm = [1.0; 0.9534; 0.9710; 0.9060]
an = [0.0; -0.1734; -0.2262; -0.2301]
v_bus = vm.*exp.(an*1im)
i_bus = y_bus*v_bus
s_bus = v_bus.*conj(i_bus)
# print the results in a data frame
df = DataFrame(v_mag = abs.(v_bus),
               v_angle = angle.(v_bus),
               p_node = real.(round.(s_bus, digits=2)),
               q_node = imag.(round.(s_bus, digits=2)))
println(df)
```

The student is invited to repeat the calculation using a real representation (i.e., using Equations (22) and (23)).

On the other hand, power flows for each line can be calculated as follows:

$$s_{km}^* = v_k^* i_{km}^{\text{line}} \quad (24)$$

$$s_{mk}^* = v_m^* i_{mk}^{\text{line}} \quad (25)$$

which is equivalent to

$$s_{km}^* = y_{km}^{\text{line}} v_k^* (v_k - v_m) \quad (26)$$

$$s_{mk}^* = y_{km}^{\text{line}} v_m^* (v_m - v_k) \quad (27)$$

Notice that, in general, $s_{km} \neq s_{mk}$ although $i_{km} = -i_{mk}$. This is because there are power loss given by

$$s_{km}^{\text{loss}} = s_{km} + s_{mk} \quad (28)$$

Figure 4 shows each variable associated to a generic distribution line connected between nodes k and m . Total

Figure 4: Power flows associated to a generic distribution line between nodes k and m .

power loss can be calculated from nodal power as given below:

$$s_{\text{loss}} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} s_k \quad (29)$$

Which can be written in matrix representation as:

$$s_{\text{loss}}^* = V_{\text{bus}}^H Y_{\text{bus}} V_{\text{bus}} \quad (30)$$

where H represents the transpose conjugate. This expression can be simplified as (31) by defining $V_{\text{bus}} = V_{\text{real}} + jV_{\text{imag}}$ and $Y_{\text{bus}} = G_{\text{bus}} + jB_{\text{bus}}$:

$$p_{\text{loss}} = V_{\text{real}}^T G_{\text{bus}} V_{\text{bus}} + V_{\text{imag}}^T G_{\text{bus}} V_{\text{imag}} \quad (31)$$

Recall that G_{bus} is weakly diagonal dominant if the graph is connected. Therefore, $G_{\text{bus}} > 0$ and hence, p_{loss} is a convex quadratic form.

Equivalently, total power loss can be calculated from the power flows in each line $(km) \in \mathcal{L}$, as given below:

$$S_{\text{loss}} = \sum_{(km) \in \mathcal{L}} S_{km} + S_{mk} \quad (32)$$

Example 7.

Let us calculate the power flows for each line in Example 6:

```

num_lines = length(L)
s_from = zeros(num_lines,1)*1im
s_to    = zeros(num_lines,1)*1im
for (i,(k,m)) in enumerate(L)
    s_from[i] = v_bus[k]*conj(1/z_branch[i]*(v_bus[k]-v_bus[m]))
    s_to[i]   = v_bus[m]*conj(1/z_branch[i]*(v_bus[m]-v_bus[k]))
end
s_loss = s_from+s_to
sf = DataFrame(line=L, p_from=real.(s_from[:]), p_to=real.(s_to[:]),
              q_from=imag.(s_from[:]), q_to=imag.(s_to[:]),
              p_loss=real.(s_loss[:]), q_loss=imag.(s_loss[:]))
println(sf)
println("Total loss = ", real(sum(s_from+s_to)))

```

Recall to execute Examples 1 and 2 to obtain the values of L , v_{bus} and Y_{bus} .

Example 8.

The node-to-branch incidence matrix A associated to a directed graph can be separated into two matrices A_{from} and A_{to} such that $A = A_{\text{from}} - A_{\text{to}}$, where A_{from} includes only the positive entries of A and A_{to} the negative entries. This simple shift allows calculating the nodal power as a function of the power flows as follows:

$$S_{\text{bus}} = A_{\text{from}}S_{\text{from}} + A_{\text{to}}S_{\text{to}} \quad (33)$$

where S_{from} is a vector that groups power flows in the graph's orientation, and S_{to} is a vector that groups the power flows in the opposite direction. The script below shows how to use these matrices.

```

A_from = 1/2*(abs.(A)+A) # only positive entries of A
A_to   = 1/2*(abs.(A)-A) # only negative entries of A
s_bus  = transpose(A_from)*s_from + transpose(A_to)*s_to

```

References

- [Garces and Rodriguez-Garcia, 2019] Garces, A. and Rodriguez-Garcia, L. (2019). An approach for nodal admittance matrix real-time estimation on dc microgrids. In *2019 IEEE Green Technologies Conference(GreenTech)*, pages 1–4.
- [Kron, 1942] Kron, G. (1942). *Tensors for circuits*. Dover Publications.
- [Molina and Rudnick, 2010] Molina, J. D. and Rudnick, H. (2010). Transmission of electric energy: a bibliographic review. *IEEE Latin America Transactions*, 8(3):245–258.